

A Study on Moral Qualities and Academic Achievements of High School Students

Ms. R. Brindha¹, Mr. K. Somasundaram²

¹M.Ed Student, ²Assistant Professor

^{1,2}RVS College of Education, Kannampalayam, Sulur, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

How to cite this paper: Ms. R. Brindha | Mr. K. Somasundaram "A Study on Moral Qualities and Academic Achievements of High School Students" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-4, June 2019, pp.1298-1303, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd25134.pdf>

IJTSRD25134

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

ABSTRACT

This study found that Moral qualities and Academic achievements of high School Students A sample of 300 high school students participated in the study. Whilst high school education are able to determine students' academic abilities on enrolment limited attention has been given to other qualities. Although there is an understanding of the qualities desired in the high school students, to date there has been limited exploration of high school students' personal qualities as they enter high school class and whether these change over time. Practical implications, limitations, and future research directions are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

School teaching Moral qualities has been largely shaped by social justice movements and educational reform initiatives that flow like tides driven by congressional flavor. Still, the profession has been cautious, even reluctant, to comply with educational reform agendas that focus exclusively on academic achievement. The time is now, however, to throw caution to the wind, not only because of the rising of political and social tides, but because continuing to practice school teaching Moral qualities from the current paradigm is detrimental to a profession that is viewed as inadequately meeting the educational needs of students—the fundamental mission of schools.

In this paper the following points to be addressed in more details

1. Review of literature
2. Analysis and data collection
3. Results
4. Conclusion

Review of Literature

Sriram, R., Verma, A., Mattu, S., Sandhu, G., & Singh, A. (2019). The paper pays attention to the father's reasons for involvement, their level of satisfaction and the emotions that emerge during the process of fathering. The authors make an attempt to look at any existing variations based on family type, gender and age of children. The paper concludes by highlighting the patterns of a father's involvement in an urban context, highlighting a father's contributions to his children's lives.

Banerjee, R., Pathak, R., & Yadav, S. (2019). The result of the study indicates positive significant impact of family relationship on spiritual intelligence.

Bhattacharya, P., & Gupta, R. K. (2019). This article focuses on such practices that foster sustainable human development in higher education institutions to enhance the quality of life of the stakeholders involved.

Maharatna, A. (2019) dominance of the Nehruvian perception (backed often tacitly by other influential quarters at the time) that people's modern mind, outlook and attitudes would emerge almost inevitably as a by-product of large-scale modern industrialization, economic development

and technological up gradation, with no need for distinctively independent (preceding or simultaneous) initiatives for the former.

Narinasamy, I., & Mamat, W. H. W. (2018). The findings highlighted teacher modelling, engaging students and pedagogical content knowledge as central themes in teacher exhibiting care to students. In displaying caring, it also accentuates the approaches the teacher embarked in developing empathy among the culturally diverse students in the classroom.

Parihar, P., Tiwari, G. K., Pandey, R., & Rai, P. K. (2018). Findings of the study showed that the male and female participants did not differ significantly in their mean scores on the five dimensions of moral foundations.. The limitations and future directions for the researchers have also been highlighted.

Sethy, S. S. (2018). Attempts to answer these questions by adopting qualitative methodology that subsumes descriptive, evaluative, and interpretative approaches. While answering these questions, it discusses significance and usefulness of academic ethics in the university set up. It examines role of academic ethics to offer quality education to students.

Further, it highlights university faculty members' roles and responsibilities toward students, colleagues, institution authorities, research works, and society at large. The paper submits that teaching in university settings is regarded as a profession, and university faculty members are regarded as professionals provided they perform their duties conforming to the teacher's code of ethics.

Choudhury, S. A., & Borooah, I. P. (2017). Counselling is a purposeful understanding of a person so as to promote self-understanding in that person. This study is based on the review of secondary literature in an attempt to highlight the utmost relevance of counselling services in an educational setting.

Variables of the Study (6)

In research, this term refers to the measurable characteristics, qualities, traits or attributes of a particular individual, object or situation being studied. Nurses use the

term variable whether they are conducting, reading or using results of qualitative or quantitative research. Researchers often refer to variable by the terms dependent or independent. Dependent variable represent outcomes of interest and they are affect by independent (i.e predictor) variables. In this study, the investigator follows independent variable and dependent variables.

An independent variable is a variable that is expected to influence the dependent variables. Its value may be changed or altered, which is independent of any other variables. Also the following demographic variables were used as independent variables.

- Gender (Male/Female).
- Medium of Study (Tamil/English)
- Type of School (Government/Private)
- Parents Income (Self Employed/Salaried)
- Locality (Urban/Rural)

Sampling Techniques

The sample which was collected from various schools located in and around Coimbatore is shown as below.

TABLE 1 LIST OF SCHOOLS USED FOR DATA COLLECTION

S. No	Name of the schools	Number of students
1	Nyruthi Vidhya Bhavan Higher Secondary School, Tiruppur	54
2	Subbiah Matriculation Higher Secondary School, Tiruppur	51
3	Jai Saradha Matriculation Higher Secondary School, Tiruppur	53
4	Jaivabai Municipal Girls Higher Secondary School, Tiruppur	49
5	Government Girls Higher Secondary School, Kunnathur	48
6	Government Higher Secondary School, Kundadam	45
	Total	300

TABLE 2 DISTRIBUTION OF SAMPLES BASED ON VARIABLES

S. No	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1	Gender	Male	190	63	300
		Female	110	37	
2	Medium of Study	Tamil	196	65	300
		English	104	35	
3	Type of School	Government	93	31	300
		Private	207	69	
4	Parents Income	Self Employed	93	31	300
		Salaried	207	69	
5	School Locality	Rural	57	19	300
		Urban	243	81	

Research Tool

Tool become another major consideration in an education research. The instrument employed for the collection of data required for the study of any problem is called tool. "Tool employ distinction way of describing and qualifying the data" the important tools of educational research include interview schedule, questionnaire, observation, rating scale, achievement test, proficiency test, psychological tests and sociogram.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is no significant level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Gender.
2. There is no significant level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Medium of study.
3. There is no significant level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Type of school.
4. There is no significant level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Parents Income.
5. There is no significant level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Locality.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Hypotheses:1

There will not be a significant level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Gender.

TABLE 3 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Gender.

S. No	Gender	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Male	190	1.4579	298	1.1563	NS
2	Female	110	1.5273			

CHART 1 LEVEL OF STUDY ON MORAL QUALITIES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR GENDER

There will not be a significant level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Medium of study.

TABLE 4 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Medium of study.

S. No	Medium of Study	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Tamil	196	1.4745	298	0.5771	NS
2	English	104	1.5096			

CHART 2 LEVEL OF STUDY ON MORAL QUALITIES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR MEDIUM OF STUDY

Hypotheses:3

There will not be a significant level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Type of school.

TABLE 5 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Type of School.

S. No	Type of School	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Government	93	1.3763	198	2.1335	S
2	Private	207	1.5072			

CHART 3 LEVEL OF STUDY ON MORAL QUALITIES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR TYPE OF SCHOOL

Hypotheses: 4

There will not be a significant level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Parents Income.

TABLE 6 NMean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Parents Occupation

S. N	Parents Income	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Self Employed	93	1.4409	178	0.6770	NS
2	Salaried	207	1.4831			

CHART 4 LEVEL OF STUDY ON MORAL QUALITIES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR PARENTS OCCUPATION

Hypotheses: 5

There will not be a significant level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Locality

TABLE 7 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of study on moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students based on their Locality.

S.No	Locality	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	Result
1	Rural	57	1.2982	90	-2.9509	S
2	Urban	243	1.5021			

CHART 5 LEVEL OF STUDY ON MORAL QUALITIES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS BASED ON THEIR LOCALITY

Summary of the Findings

A study on high school students' level of moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students was studied and the findings reveal that **there is no significant in moral qualities and academic achievements** of high school students with respect to **Gender, Medium of Study, Parents occupation.**

A study on high school students' level of moral qualities and academic achievements of high school students was studied and the findings reveal that **there is a significant in moral qualities and academic achievements** of high school students with respect to **Type of School and Locality.**

Conclusion

There is also some evidence to suggest that perceptions of the classroom academic motivation may exert a direct effect on outcome measures as well. The use of multilevel data analysis procedures enables researchers to test the predictive influence of classroom academic motivations at both the individual and classroom levels. In this research, learning environments may be characterized as having either a greater mastery or performance focus (or a simultaneous focus on both mastery and performance) when students' perceptions of the academic motivation are aggregated to the classroom or school level.

Evidence to date indicates that approximately 5% to 35% of the variation in students' academic motivation perceptions is related to classroom differences. When added to the analyses, mean perceptions of the classroom academic motivation explain variance in some outcome measures not explained by individual perceptions of classroom academic motivations, personal achievement goals, or student background characteristics.

References

- [1] Alhadabi, A., Aldhafri, S., Alkharusi, H., Al-Harthy, I., Alrajhi, M., & AlBarashdi, H. (2019). Modelling parenting styles, moral intelligence, academic self-efficacy and learning motivation among adolescents in grades 7-11. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 1-21.
- [2] Acharya, S. (2005). The ethical climate in academic dentistry in India: faculty and student perceptions. *Journal of dental education*, 69(6), 671-680.
- [3] Achugar, M., & Carpenter, B. D. (2014). Tracking movement toward academic language in multilingual classrooms. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 14, 60-71.
- [4] Assor, A., & Tal, K. (2012). When parents' affection depends on child's achievement: Parental conditional positive regard, self-aggrandizement, shame and coping in adolescents. *Journal of adolescence*, 35(2), 249-260.
- [5] Banerjee, R., Pathak, R., & Yadav, S. (2019). Family Relationship and Spiritual Intelligence: With Reference to Students of Professional Courses. Available at SSRN 3307724.
- [6] Bernardo, A. B., & Ismail, R. (2010). Social perceptions of achieving students and achievement goals of students in Malaysia and the Philippines. *Social Psychology of Education*, 13(3), 385-407.
- [7] Bhattacharya, P., & Gupta, R. K. (2019). Towards Human Sustainability in Higher Education by Adopting a Positive Approach. *Advanced Science, Engineering and Medicine*, 11(1-2), 133-140.
- [8] Brasche, I., & Thorn, B. (2018). Addressing dimensions of "The Great Moral Wrong": How inequity in music education is polarizing the academic potential of Australian students. *Arts Education Policy Review*, 119(3), 124-136.
- [9] Brimi, H. (2009). Academic instructors or moral guides? Moral education in America and the teacher's dilemma. *The Clearing House: A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas*, 82(3), 125-130.
- [10] Butler, R., Ho, C., & Vincent, E. (2017). "Tutored within an inch of their life": morality and 'old' and 'new' middle class identities in Australian schools. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 43(14), 2408-2422.
- [11] Chand, V. S., & Amin-Choudhury, G. (2006). Teachers and socio-educational entrepreneurship: Competence as a consequence. *The Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 15(2), 97-114.
- [12] Choudhury, S. A., & Barooah, I. P. (2016). Character strengths and academic achievement in undergraduate college students. *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology*, 7(1), 76.
- [13] Choudhury, S. A., & Borooah, I. P. (2017). Character strengths and academic achievements of undergraduate college students of Guwahati, Assam. *Space and Culture, India*, 5(1), 49-64.
- [14] Duckworth, A. L., & Yeager, D. S. (2015). Measurement matters: Assessing personal qualities other than cognitive ability for educational purposes. *Educational Researcher*, 44(4), 237-251.
- [15] Fang, L., Sun, R. C., & Yuen, M. (2017). "Be useful to society": parental academic involvement in rural to urban migrant children's education in China. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 18(3), 361-371.
- [16] Gillham, J., Adams-Deutsch, Z., Werner, J., Reivich, K., Coulter-Heindl, V., Linkins, M., ... & Contero, A. (2011). Character strengths predict subjective well-being during adolescence. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 6(1), 31-44.
- [17] Gitanjali, B. (2004). Academic dishonesty in Indian medical colleges. *Journal of postgraduate medicine*, 50(4), 281.
- [18] Jeynes, W. H. (2009). The relationship between biblical literacy, academic achievement, and school behavior among Christian-and public-school students. *Journal of Research on Christian Education*, 18(1), 36-55.
- [19] Jeynes, W. H. (2019). A meta-analysis on the relationship between character education and student achievement and behavioral outcomes. *Education and Urban Society*, 51(1), 33-71.
- [20] Lapsley, D., & Woodbury, R. (2016). Moral-character development for teacher education. *Action in teacher education*, 38(3), 194-206.
- [21] Maharatna, A. (2019). India's Educational Thinking, Aims and School Curriculum: A Critical Look. In *The*

Indian Metamorphosis (pp. 91-131). Palgrave Macmillan, Singapore.

[22] Mishra, S., & Suar, D. (2010). Does corporate social responsibility influence firm performance of Indian companies?. Journal of business ethics, 95(4), 571-601.

[23] Muralidharan, K., & Sundararaman, V. (2011). Teacher performance pay: Experimental evidence from India. Journal of political Economy, 119(1), 39-77.

[24] Narinasamy, I., & Mamat, W. H. W. (2018). Caring teacher in developing empathy in moral education. MOJES: Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Sciences, 1(1), 1-19.

[25] Parihar, P., Tiwari, G. K., Pandey, R., & Rai, P. K. (2018). Assessing the Relative Impacts of Gender and Educational Levels on the Moral Foundations of the Students.

PERSONAL DATA SHEET APPENDICES PROFORMA FOR BASIC DATA

1. Name of the Student :
2. Name of the School :
3. Gender : Male Female
4. Medium of Study : Tamil English
5. Type of School : Government Private
6. Parents Income : Self Employed Salaried
7. Locality : Rural Urban

INSTRUCTIONS

- There are some statement below. Each statement is followed by multiple choice i.e Yes,/No.
- Read each Statement carefully.
- After reading each statement mark your response in the appropriate column pitting at tick mark.

S.NO	QUESTIONARIE	YES	NO
1	I like learning Moral qualities.		
2	I will persist when facing difficulties in Moral qualities.		
3	I like listening to Moral qualities related speech.		
4	I like reading Moral qualities articles.		
5	I feel more confident in Moral qualities learning compared with my classmates		
6	I work on my Moral qualities assignments according to a planned schedule.		
7	I study Moral qualities diligently for potential development in the future.		
8	In order to know the recent development in my major, I study Moral qualities diligently		
9	Moral qualities is a very important tool for life so I study it diligently		
10	In order to get an ideal life in the future I study Moral qualities diligently		
11	Moral qualities learning takes great advantage on the future life		
12	I treat Moral values examination as an evaluation of what I have learned about Moral qualities.		
13	I like Moral qualities stories.		
14	I am excited when I have accomplished a difficult task in Moral qualities learning.		
15	I can finish my Moral qualities actively		
16	1) I study Moral qualities hard for the praise of the teacher.		
17	My teacher helps me to improve my Moral qualities.		
18	My Family always give lot of new words to understand Moral qualities.		
19	My teachers encourage me to participate in Moral qualities competitions		
20	I like to follow my teachers who have some sense of moral qualities		